

ISic2765

I.Sicily inscription 2765

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication; building
(?)

Material

volcanic (from Fuardo)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334102

1. [— — — Ἀπόλλ]ωνος

2. [— — — —]αν²⁷[ἀνέθηκ]αν(?); [ἐποίησ]αν(?)²⁷.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645162

PHI 334102

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

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Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 1

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